

EFFECTS OF *GARCINIA KOLA* SEED POWDER ON SERUM LEVEL OF FSH, LH AND TESTOSTERONE OF MALE ALBINO RATS EXPOSED TO EXOGENOUS HORMONES ADMINISTRATION.

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ABSTRACT.

The study was carried out to investigate the effect of *Garcinia kola* Seed Powder inclusions on serum levels of follicle stimulating hormone, Luteinizing hormone, and testosterone of male albino rats exposed to exogenous hormone (Menotrophin and Testosterone) administration. The study investigated the adnohypophyseal-gonadal hormone interactions in male Albino rats administered with exogenous hormone while receiving doses of *Garcinia kola* seed powder. The study was carried out in two phases. Phase one was the administration of exogenous hormones (Menotrophin and Testosterone) and 18 male albino rats assigned into three treatment groups of 6 rats each were used. Phase two of the study consists of administration of *Garcinia kola* seed powder in the same way as was done in phase one of the study. The experiment was terminated after 6 weeks of treatment. The result obtained showed a significant ($P<0.05$) increase in serum gonadotrophins and testosterone levels relative to control rats on administration of menotrophin but a decrease in serum testosterone and an increase in gonadotrophins on administration of exogenous testosterone. The feeding of *Garcinia kola* seed powder to the rats however, caused no-significant ($P>0.05$) increase in serum gonadotrophin but a significant ($P<0.05$) reduction in testosterone levels of male albino rats exposed to menotrophins. There was also significant ($P<0.05$) reduction in both serum gonadotrophin and testosterone levels of male albino rats exposed to exogenous testosterone. The findings of this study revealed that there seem to be negative feed back control on testosterone secretion by gonadotrophin in rats treated with *Garcinia kola* seed Powder and that the detrimental effect of *Garcinia kola* seed powder on the testis may not be reversed by administration of exogenous testosterone.

KEYWORDS: *Garcinia kola* Powder, FSH, LH, Testosterone, exogenous hormones.

INTRODUCTION

Testosterone and androsterone induce puberty in the male and maintains male secondary (Muscular development, deepening of voice, agonistic behaviour) characteristics (Elizabeth, 2000). Testosterone is secreted mainly by the interstitial (Leydig) cells of the testes under the influence of pulsatile secretion of Luteinizing hormone (LH) from anterior pituitary gland (Tripathi, 2001). Testosterone inhibits gonadotrophin secretion by a negative feedback mechanism similar to that of ovarian hormones in female (Stanley, 2005). Follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) is mainly responsible for promotion of spermatogenesis in tubular sertoli cells (Tripathi, 2001). Administration of 2 α -methyl dihydrotestosterone and fluoroxymersterone in males produced a dose related decline in plasma testosterone level over several days (Davis *et al*; 1965). Administration of 20mg /day of fluoroxymersterone caused a slight reduction in LH whereas 50mg/day administration reduced plasma to undetectable level (Swerdloff and Odell, 1968). Franchimont (1966) reported a sharp decline in plasma LH following a single intramuscular injection of 50mg of testosterone propionate in normal subject. There was no significant change in plasma FSH in above trials. Plasma LH level had significantly fallen on administration of 25mg /day of testosterone i/m in three normal subjects but FSH fell significantly in one, marginally in another and rose in the third (Peterson *et al.*, 1968). Heller *et al.* (1970) gave testosterone propionate 100mg daily for five days to two subjects, LH fell but no fall in FSH was detected.

Evidences have shown that apart from the long feedback exerted on gonadotrophins by androgens and estrogens, pituitary gonadotrophins secretion may be influenced by a short feedback system whereby the gonadotrophins may modify its own rate of secretion directly. This concept was observed and reported by Martini (1970) for FSH and (Motta *et al.*, 1969). The availability of antiandrogens, which act by competing with androgens for their receptors

sites in target cells (Neumann and Wallrobe, 1966) has led to a limited number of studies of their effect in animals. Franchimont (1971) observed a fall in plasma levels of FSH and LH in man administered with 300mg Cyproterone acetate (antiandrogenic agent). In contrast Neumann *et al* (1970) found an increase in LH and testosterone Urinary excretion.

Braide *et al* (2003) reported a significant reduction in serum testosterone levels of male rats following administration of *Garcinia kola* seed extract. (Ibekwe *et al*. 2007) reported a reduced serum testosterone level of rats administered with crude flavonoid extract of *Garcinia kola* seeds.

The multi-purpose medicinal uses of *Garcinia kola* seeds calls for investigation into its effects on reproductive parameters. The competitive protein-binding test measures plasma or serum testosterone level and when combined with serum gonadotrophin levels (FSH, LH) reliably aids evaluation of gonadal dysfunction in males and females. This study was set forth to ascertain whether exposure to exogenous hormones administration will ameliorate the detrimental effect of *Garcinia kola* seeds on reproduction and whether hypo secretion of testosterone observed in this study is primary or secondary in origin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Thirty six (36) young male albino rats weighing between 120 and 150 g were purchased from animal house in the Department of Pharmacology and Zoology University of Calabar. The rats were housed in group of 9 per cage in animal house Department of Pharmacology for a period of 14 days for proper acclimatization. The rats were maintained on vital growers mash under 12 h light and 12 h dark cycle with ambient temperature of $23 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity of 50% Clean tap water was given ad libitum.

Preparation of *Garcinia kola* Powder.

Garcinia kola seeds weighing about 2000g were purchased from local market within Calabar municipal council Area. The seeds were sun dried for a whole day to ease off the removal of the testa. The seeds were sliced to increase the surface area of drying. The drying was done in an electric oven (Gallenkamp grade,, USA) After drying to a constant weight, the seeds were ground to powder by a grinding machine in Watt market Calabar. *Garcinia kola* seed powder was then administered to the rats at 30% inclusion level in the feed.

Animals and Animal Treatments

A total of 18 male rats assigned into three treatment groups of six rats each were used in phase one of this study. Treatment group one rats received basal feed (vital growers mash) at 54g/kg body weight of rats. Treatment two and three in addition received 2.6mg and 2.5mg of menotrophin and testosterone per kg body weight of rat respectively. The treatment was terminated at the end of six weeks. The rats were euthanized by chloroform inhalation and blood samples collected via cardiac puncture. The blood was allowed to stand for one hour to clot. The clotted blood was spun at 5000rpm and the serum collected was assayed for FSH, LH and testosterone concentration in the various treatment groups.

The second phase of this study involves the inclusion of 30% *Garcinia kola* seed powder in the basal feed of the rat. The diet produced was fed to the rats at the rate of 54g/kg body weight and water was given ad libitum. Treatment group one received *Garcinia kola* seed diet at the rate of 54g/kg body weight of rats.

Treatment groups two and three received in addition 2.6mg and 2.5mg of menotrophin and testosterone per kg body weight of rats respectively. Treatments were terminated after six weeks, serum collected and assayed for FSH LH and testosterone concentrations in the various treatments administered.

Microwell hormonal enzyme Immuno assay

The microwell hormonal enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELIZA) is a solid phase enzyme immuno assay based on the sandwich principle. Two separate antibodies directed against distinct antigenic determinants of the hormone molecules are utilized in the assay. The specific hormone in the test sample reacts simultaneously with one antibody immobilized on the microwell surface and with another antibody conjugated to horseradish peroxidase enzyme. So an Ab-Ag-enzyme complex is formed on the microwell surface.

The unbound conjugate is removed by washing and the colour development reagent (substrates) are added. Upon exposure to the enzyme, a colour change takes place. The intensity of the colour reflects the amount of bound anti-hormone enzyme conjugate and is proportional to the level of hormone in the test sample within the dynamic range of the assay. After stopping the reaction, the resulting colour is measured using a spectrophotometer at a wave length of 450nm. Using a standard curve obtained by plotting the hormone levels of reference standard against the corresponding absorbance, the hormone levels of the concurrently run test samples and controls can now be determined. The detailed procedure is as described by Colin *et al* (1999)

RESULTS

Table 1: Serum levels of LH, FSH and testosterone of male albino rats administered with menotrophin and testosterone.

Treatment groups.		Hormonal Levels		
		LH(mIU/ML)	FSH(mIU/ML)	Testosterone (ng/ml).
1.	Basal Feed (control).	0.30±0.04 ^a	0.20 ± 0.03 ^a	0.25±0.03 ^a
2.	Menotrophin i/m 2.6mg/kg b.wt	0.70±0.10 ^b	0.53±0.09 ^b	0.70±0.09 ^b
3.	Testosterone i/m 2.5mg/kg b.wt	18.30±1.38 ^c	12.90±2.14 ^c	0.20±0.04 ^a

Means in the same column with different superscripts are significantly (P<0.05) different from control.

Table 2. Garcinia Kola Seed diet and exogenous hormone administration effects on serum LH, FSH and testosterone levels of male albino rats.

Treatment groups.		Hormonal Levels		
		LH(mIU/ML)	FSH(mIU/ML)	Testosterone (ng/ml).
1	<i>G.kola</i> diet (54g/kg)	0.45±0.04 ^a	0.22±0.02 ^a	0.10±0.02 ^a
2.	G.K.D+menotrophin i/m 2.6mg/kg b.wt	0.90±0.10 ^b	0.90±0.11 ^b	0.45±0.05 ^b
3.	G.K.D.+ Testosterone i/m2.5mg/kg b.wt.	1.90±0.14 ^c	0.70±0.11 ^b	0.15±0.02 ^a

Means in the same column with different superscripts are significantly (P<0.05) different from control treatment.

Table 1. presented the serum levels of luteinizing hormone LH, Follicle stimulating hormone FSH and testosterone of male albino rats administered with exogenous (menotrophin and testosterone) hormones. The result obtained showed significant (P<0.05) increase in serum levels of the three hormones under investigation on administration of menotrophin. The administration of testosterone however, produced significant (P<0.05) increase in serum levels of LH and FSH but no significant (P>0.05) reduction in the levels of endogenous testosterone relative to control rats.

Garcinia kola diet and exogenous hormone administration effects were presented in Table 2. The result revealed significant (P<0.05) increase in serum levels of LH, FSH and testosterone when administered with menotrophin. There was also significant (P<0.05) increase in serum levels of LH and FSH but no significant (P>0.05) reduction in the level of endogenous testosterone of male albino rats administered with exogenous testosterone.

The results obtained in the two phases of the study when compared showed no significant ($P>0.05$) increase (0.90 ± 0.10 and 0.90 ± 0.11 mIU/ml) in serum levels of LH and FSH relative to control (0.70 ± 0.10 and 0.53 ± 0.09) mIU/ml rats treated with *Garcinia kola* seed diet. There was however a significant ($P<0.05$) reduction (0.45 ± 0.05 ng/ml) in serum level of testosterone of male albino rats exposed to *Garcinia kola* seed diet relative to control (0.70 ± 0.09 ng/ml). *Garcinia kola* seed diet however caused significant ($P<0.05$) reductions (1.90 ± 0.14 and 0.70 ± 0.11 mIU/ml) in serum levels of male albino rats exposed to exogenous hormone relative to control (18.30 ± 1.38 and 12.90 ± 2.14 mIU/ml) rats. The phases when compared also revealed no- significant ($P>0.05$) reduction (0.15 ± 0.02 ng/ml) in serum level of endogenous testosterone of male albino rats relative to control (0.20 ± 0.04 ng/ml) rats treated with *Garcinia kola* seed diet exogenous testosterone.

DISCUSSION

The reduction in endogenous serum testosterone level of male albino rats treated with 30% *Garcinia kola* seed powder as observed in this study agrees with the finding of Braide *et al* (2003) who reported a significant reduction in serum testosterone of male albino rats administered with crude alkaloid extract of *Garcinia kola* seed. This was supported by the report of Ibekwe *et al*. (2007) who observed a decrease in serum testosterone levels of male Albino rats administered with crude flavonoid extract of *Garcinia kola* seed. These lend credence to the earlier observation of Udoh (1998) on effect of methanolic extract of *Garcinia kola* seed and Piper guinensis leave on reproductive organs. He reported testicular atrophy and spermatogenesis arrest.

The increased levels of serum LH and FSH as observed in this study on administration of menotrophin agreed with the findings of Martini, (1970) and Motta *et al*. (1969) who reported the ability of gonadotrophin modifying its secretion on administration of exogenous menotrophin through short feedback system. Gonadotrophins act, synergistically to augment serum endogenous gonadotrophin levels by short feedback loop but can bring down its level by negative feedback mechanism.

Administration of exogenous testosterone in this study produced significant increase in serum levels of LH and FSH. This is at variance with the report of Stanley (2005) who reported an inhibitory effect of gonadotrophin by testosterone administration. This increase in LH resulted to a decrease in serum endogenous testosterone. The high level of LH probably caused a decline in testosterone by its action on Leydig cells which control the secretion of testosterone.

The feeding of *Garcinia kola* seed diet to these rats produced significant reduction in serum levels of LH and FSH but no significant changes in serum levels of endogenous testosterone. *Garcinia kola* seed may be seen as antiandrogenic agent capable of reducing the serum level of LH and FSH. This agreed with the report of Franchimont (1971) who observed a fall in plasma FSH and LH in man administered with 300mg Cyproterone acetate.

The findings in this study showed that *Garcinia kola* seed diet caused non-significant increase in serum gonadotrophin of male albino rats but significant reduction in serum levels of testosterone which could not be reversed by administration of exogenous testosterone.

CONCLUSION

The significant reduction on serum testosterone levels of male albino rats even when exposed to exogenous testosterone seem to support the fact that detrimental effect of *Garcinia kola* seed on the testes may not be reversed by administration of exogenous testosterone. There is need therefore to exercise caution while using *Garcinia kola* seed for therapeutic purposes in male. The increased level of gonadotrophin caused by *Garcinia kola* seed administration which led to decline in serum testosterone seemed to support the existence of negative feedback control and hence adohypophyseal-gonadal interaction. This points to the fact that this reduction may be secondary in origin.

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